

AntifragiCity News

Rethinking Urban Mobility Beyond Resilience

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Dear reader,

We're excited to share the latest updates from AntifragiCity.

In this edition, we invite you to watch our new video, meet the professionals driving our work forward, explore our latest resources and research insights, and discover ways to get involved in shaping the future of urban mobility.

Let's get started!

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Cities move us. Every day, we commute, connect, and navigate urban life. But when disruption hits, resilience alone is no longer enough. **What if cities could learn from disruption and grow stronger because of it? This is the idea behind *antifragility*.**

At AntifragiCity, we're rethinking urban mobility across Europe. Bringing together 13 partners across 8 countries, we are designing systems that don't just recover, but adapt, improve, and evolve through disruption.

Our approach combines:

- **Technologies** to detect and assess disruptions
- **Real-world testing** in four [pilot cities](#)
- **Citizen participation** at the centre of decision-making
- **Data-driven insights** for better urban planning

What we learn contributes to **European research and policy**, helping cities become more sustainable, inclusive, and prepared for the unexpected.

[Watch the video](#)

Voices of AntifragiCity

Introducing: Voices of AntifragiCity

We spoke with six of our partners to hear about their roles, motivations, and what excites them most about the work ahead.

From transport analysis and citizen participation to communication and outreach, these interviews offer an **inside look at the expertise behind AntifragiCity**:

💬 “I am especially excited about bringing together three types of knowledge: what citizens say, what experts know, and what the data tells us about how cities behave in real life.” [Ali Ghoroghi, Cardiff University](#)

💬 “While current systems have been built on trying to avoid disruptions, we are embracing them and trying to build cities that can learn and become better and stronger through disruptions.” [Theocharis Vlachopanagiotis, Rhoé](#)

💬 “AntifragiCity is about hearing what cities are today, and what they might need in the future, not only from experts, but also from citizens.” [Lisa Verhasselt, LISER](#)

Featuring contributions from: Ali Ghoroghi · Nancy Tzioutziou · Theocharis Vlachopanagiotis · Katerina Moschopoulou · Lisa Verhasselt · Antonis Sapountzis

[Watch the full playlist](#)

Explore our Latest Milestones

[Women shaping the future of urban mobility](#)

To mark International Women's Day 2026, we brought together insights from women across AntifragiCity, highlighting their experiences and contributions to more inclusive, diverse, and resilient research and innovation. [Read the full article](#).

[Have your say: Social Acceptability Survey](#)

During heatwaves, floods, fuel shortages, or infrastructure failures, cities may need to prioritise certain transport modes. This survey explores how acceptable these responses are. [Take the survey](#); it takes 10 mins, is anonymous, and is available in English, Slovak, Ukrainian, French, and Dutch (Greek coming soon).

[New tool: KPIs Definition Framework](#)

We've developed a KPIs definition tool that enables cities to define and customise KPIs based on strategic vision, objectives, and real-world applicability. [Access the tool](#).

[Share your thoughts with us](#)

Following Bratislava, Citizens' Forums in Larissa and Thessaloniki brought citizens into the conversation to co-design solutions for antifragile cities. You can also [make your voice heard](#).

Discover our latest deliverables

These resources advance our understanding of antifragile urban mobility:

- [Dissemination, communication and engagement plans](#): Our plan for sharing our research and engaging stakeholders across Europe.
- [Urban event mapping](#): A pan-European mapping of urban disruptions, revealing that transport issues dominate the risk

landscape.

- **Establishing urban states of equilibrium**: A theoretical framework for measuring whether mobility systems are moving towards antifragility.
- **KPIs and framework development**: An adaptive framework with 2,540 reviewed indicators for measuring antifragile urban mobility.
- **Ontology**: A semantic foundation for modelling antifragile urban mobility systems, integrating with digital twins and AI.

[Visit the Deliverables page](#)

Let's continue building antifragile cities together.

Thank you for being part of the AntifragiCity community.

Follow us and stay connected:

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